

Synthesis, characterization and *in vivo* anthelmintic activity of some novel *N*-Mannich bases of benzimidazoles

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Abstract : As a part of ongoing efforts towards finding novel anthelmintic agents, *N*-Mannich bases of benzimidazole were obtained by condensation of substituted secondary amines and aldehyde in ethanol. These compounds were identified on the basis of melting point range, R_f values, elemental analysis, IR and ^1H NMR spectral analysis. The synthetic work is fruitless without performing biological activities, so the newly synthesized compounds were screened for pharmacological activity. Anthelmintic activity was carried out against *Eudrilus* species of earthworms.

Keywords : Mannich bases, benzimidazole, anthelmintic activity.

Introduction

Synthetic compounds containing Mannich bases having potential therapeutic values are widely used in pharmaceutical industries. The literature revealed that the compounds possessing Mannich bases showed significant biological activities and benzimidazole nucleus is also a constituent of many of the bioactive compounds that exhibits wide range of biological activities, like anthelmintic¹⁻⁴, antibacterial^{5,6}, antifungal⁷, anti-inflammatory⁸, antiviral⁹ as well as antitumour activity¹⁰⁻¹². Research in this area is still unexplored and is directed towards the synthesis of compounds with enhanced biological activity. The present work is focused on the synthesis of some novel *N*-Mannich bases of benzimidazoles due to importance of this class of compounds which has found application in medicinal chemistry as anthelmintic agents.

Results and discussion

N-Mannich bases of benzimidazole were obtained by condensation of substituted secondary amines and aldehyde in ethanol as shown in Scheme 1. The structures of the newly synthesized compounds **1a-e**, **2a-c** and **3a-b** have been elucidated on the basis of elemental analysis, m.p. determination and spectral (FTIR and ^1H NMR) studies.

Anthelmintic activity :

All the compounds were screened for their anthelmintic activity against *Eudrilus* sp. at 4 mg/ml in Tween 80 (0.5%) and distilled water¹³. The paralyzing and death times were noted and their mean was calculated for triplicate sets. The results of anthelmintic activity are shown in Table 1. From the results, it was concluded that many compounds showed significant anthelmintic activity against *Eudrilus* species. A comparable study of anthelmintic activity of compounds has revealed that compounds **1e**, **2b**

Table 1. Anthelmintic activity of compounds against *Eudrilus* sp.

Compd.	Mean paralyzing time (min) ^a	Mean death time (min) ^a
1a	15.67 ± 0.45	26.45 ± 0.03
1b	13.64 ± 0.10	22.98 ± 0.21
1e	11.28 ± 0.87	21.50 ± 1.34
1d	13.56 ± 0.51	25.02 ± 0.86
1e	7.91 ± 0.10	17.67 ± 0.10
2a	14.67 ± 0.10	25.34 ± 0.21
2b	8.45 ± 1.63	17.92 ± 0.78
2c	13.33 ± 0.70	25.89 ± 0.00
3a	6.15 ± 0.50	15.67 ± 0.27
3b	14.32 ± 0.19	28.69 ± 0.83
Albendazole	11.02 ± 0.69	23.02 ± 0.65

^aData are given as mean ± S.D. (n = 3); S.D. = standard deviation.

Scheme 1. Synthesis of *N*-Mannich bases of benzimidazoles.

and 3a possessed significant activity against *Eudrilus* species in comparison to standard drug Albendazole and other compounds showed low to moderate anthelmintic activity.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were procured from Qualigens® Fine Chemicals, Mumbai and Central Drug House (P.) Ltd., New Delhi. All the melting points were determined in open capillary tubes and are uncorrected. Thin layer chromatography using silica gel G (E. Merck) plates was used to access the reactions and purity of synthesized compounds. Satisfactory C, H, N analyses were obtained for all the compounds on a Carlo Erba EA 1108 elemental analyzer. The λ_{max} of synthesized compounds were scanned on UV-Visible spectrophotometer Pharma Spec-1700. The IR spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer spectrum RXI FTIR system in KBr pellets and notewor-

thy absorption levels (cm^{-1}) are listed. ^1H NMR spectra were run on Bruker Avance II 400 NMR at 300 MHz in $\text{DMSO}-d_6$ as solvent and TMS as an internal standard.

Benzimidazole (1): *o*-Phenylenediamine (1.08 g, 10.0 mmol) was placed in a 100 ml flask and to it was added 0.7 g (0.64 ml, 13.6 mmol) of 85% formic acid. The mixture was heated on a water bath for 2 h at 100 °C, cooled, and 10% sodium hydroxide solution was added slowly with constant rotation of the flask, until the mixture was just alkaline to litmus. Crude benzimidazole was filtered off at the pump, washed with ice cooled water, drained well and washed again with cold water. The crude product was dissolved in boiling water, decolorizing carbon was added to it, and the mixture was digested for 15 min. Filtered rapidly at the pump through a preheated buckner funnel, the filtrate was cooled to about 10 °C, the product was filtered off, washed with cold water and

dried to give pure benzimidazole (compound 1) (79.66%), m.p. 171 °C (lit. 171–172 °C)¹⁴.

2-Methylbenzimidazole (2) : Mixture of *o*-phenylenediamine (1.81 g, 10.0 mmol), 6.67 ml of water, 1.03 ml (10.0 mmol) of acetic acid was heated together under reflux of 45 min. The cooled reaction mixture was made distinctly basic by the gradual addition of concentrated ammonia solution, the precipitated product was collected and recrystallized from 10% aqueous ethanol to give 2-methylbenzimidazole (compound 2), (52.60%), m.p. 175 °C (lit. 176 °C)¹⁴.

2-Benzylbenzimidazole (3) : Mixture of *o*-phenylenediamine (1.81 g, 10.0 mmol), 6.7 ml of water, 4.1 g (10.0 mmol) of phenylacetic acid were refluxed for 45 min. The cooled reaction mixture was made distinctly basic by the gradual addition of concentrated ammonia solution, precipitated product was collected, recrystallized from 40% aqueous ethanol to give 2-benzylbenzimidazole (compound 3) (53.59%), m.p. 190 °C (lit. 191 °C)¹⁴.

***N,N*-Diethylaminomethyl-1*H*-benzimidazole (1a)** : To a solution containing benzimidazole (compound 1) (1.18 g, 10.0 mmol) in 20 ml of ethanol, 1.03 ml (10.0 mmol) of diethyl amine and 0.27 ml (10 mmol) of 37% formaldehyde were added with constant stirring for 1 h. The reaction mixture was refluxed for 20 min. On cooling, the product formed was filtered, dried in vacuum and recrystallized from ethanol to give compound 1a (64.53%), m.p. 145–147 °C (Found : C, 70.87; H, 8.32; N, 20.57. Calcd. for C₁₂H₁₇N₃ : C, 70.90; H, 8.37; N, 20.60%); UV λ_{max} (DMSO) : 275.0 nm; IR (KBr) ν_{max} : 3061.6 (Ar-C-H stretch), 2858.9 (C-H sym. stretch CH₂), 1587.4 (ring C=C stretch), 1478.0 (C=N stretch), 1365.3 (C-N stretch of 3° amine), 1125.6 cm⁻¹ (C-N stretch); ¹H NMR (DMSO-*d*₆) δ : 1.06 ppm (6H, t, (CH₃)₂), 2.44 (4H, q, (CH₂)₂), 4.89 (2H, s, CH₂), 7.25 (2H, d, ArH), 7.63 (2H, t, ArH), 8.05 (1H, s, ArH).

***N,N*-Dimethylaminomethyl-1*H*-benzimidazole (1b)** : To a solution containing benzimidazole (compound 1) (1.18 g, 10.0 mmol) in 20 ml of ethanol, 0.50 g (10 mmol) of dimethylamine and 0.27 ml (10 mmol) of 37% formaldehyde were added with stirring for 1 h. The reaction mixture was refluxed for 20 min. On cooling, the product

formed was filtered, dried in vacuum and recrystallized from ethanol to give compound 1b (62.27%), m.p. 139–141 °C (Found : C, 68.53; H, 7.39; N, 24.03. Calcd. for C₁₀H₁₃N₃ : C, 68.57; H, 7.42; N, 24.00%); UV λ_{max} (DMSO) : 275.0 nm; IR (KBr) ν_{max} : 3049.0 (Ar-C-H stretch), 2836.5 (C-H sym. stretch CH₂), 1497.6 (ring C=C stretch), 1458.0 (C=N stretch), 1385.3 (C-N stretch 3° amine), 1155.0 cm⁻¹ (C-N stretch); ¹H NMR (DMSO-*d*₆) δ : 2.20 ppm (6H, s, (CH₃)₂), 4.72 (2H, s, CH₂), 7.60 (2H, d, ArH), 7.75 (2H, t, ArH), 8.01 (1H, s, ArH).

***N,N*-Diphenylaminomethyl-1*H*-benzimidazole (1c)** : To a solution containing benzimidazole (compound 1) (1.18 g, 10 mmol) in 20 ml of ethanol, 1.69 g (10 mmol) of diphenyldiamine and 0.27 ml (10 mmol) of 37% formaldehyde were added with stirring for 1 h. The reaction mixture was refluxed for 20 min. On cooling, the product formed was filtered, dried in vacuum and recrystallized from methanol to give compound 1c (64.88%), m.p. 202–204 °C (Found : C, 80.22; H, 5.65; N, 14.09. Calcd. for C₂₀H₁₇N₃ : C, 80.26; H, 5.68; N, 14.06%); UV λ_{max} (DMSO) : 299.5 nm; IR (KBr) ν_{max} : 3040.0 (Ar-C-H stretch), 2799.4 (C-H sym. stretch CH₂), 1593.1 (ring C=C stretch), 1494.1 (C=N stretch), 1309.8 (C-N stretch 3° amine), 1274.5 cm⁻¹ (C-N stretch); ¹H NMR (DMSO-*d*₆) δ : 5.59 ppm (2H, s, CH₂), 6.98 (2H, t, C₆H₅), 7.05 (4H, t, C₆H₅), 7.13 (4H, d, C₆H₅), 7.33 (2H, t, ArH), 7.69 (2H, d, ArH), 8.10 (1H, s, ArH).

4-[1*H*-Benzimidazol-yl-(*p*-hydroxybenzal)amino]benzoic acid (1d) : Equimolar quantities of benzimidazole (compound 1) (1.18 g, 10.0 mmol), *p*-aminobenzoic acid (1.37 g, 10 mmol), *p*-hydroxybenzaldehyde (1.22 g, 10.0 mmol) were weighed and refluxed for 10 h using 15 ml of ethanol as a solvent. Crude product was filtered off, washed several times with water, purified by recrystallization with absolute ethanol to give compound 1d (70.11%), m.p. 171–173 °C (Found : C, 68.19; H, 4.42; N, 16.50. Calcd. for C₂₂H₁₇N₃O₄ : C, 68.21; H, 4.39; N, 16.53%); UV λ_{max} (CHCl₃) : 234.0 nm; IR (KBr) ν_{max} : 3363.7 (O-H stretch), 3066.8 (Ar-C-H stretch), 2873.9 (O-H stretch -COOH), 1681.0 (C=O stretch -CHO), 1594.3 (ring C=C stretch), 1490.3, 1422.2 (C-C stretch skeletal bands), 1448.4 (C=N stretch),

1171.9 cm^{-1} (C–N stretch); ^1H NMR (DMSO- d_6) δ : 4.54 ppm (1H, s, N–H), 5.16 (1H, s, O–H), 6.57 (2H, d, $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{COOH}$), 6.69 (1H, s, C–H), 6.85 (2H, d, *p*-hydroxybenzaldehyde), 7.26 (2H, t, ArH), 7.50 (1H, d, *p*-hydroxybenzaldehyde), 7.65 (2H, d, ArH), 7.92 (2H, d, $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{COOH}$), 8.09 (1H, s, ArH), 10.14 (1H, s, –CHO), 10.86 (1H, s, –COOH).

4-[1H-Benzimidazol-yl-(*p*-methoxybenzal) methylamino]-benzoic acid (1e) : Equimolar quantities of benzimidazole (compound 1) (1.18 g, 10.0 mmol), *p*-aminobenzoic acid (1.37 g, 10.0 mmol), *p*-methoxybenzaldehyde (1.209 g, 10.0 mmol) were weighed and refluxed for 12 h using 15 ml of ethanol as a solvent. Crude product was filtered off, washed several times with water, purified by recrystallization with absolute ethanol to give compound 1e (67.74%), m.p. 182–184 °C (Found : C, 68.81; H, 4.70; N, 10.44. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{23}\text{H}_{19}\text{N}_3\text{O}_4$: C, 68.82; H, 4.74; N, 10.47%); UV λ_{max} (CHCl_3) : 267.0 nm; IR (KBr) ν_{max} : 3342.7 (O–H stretch), 2979.2 (Ar–C–H stretch), 2979.2 (C–H stretch of –OCH₃), 2665.8 (O–H stretch –COOH), 1683.0 (C=O stretch –CHO), 1631.0 (C=O stretch –COOH), 1593.6 (ring C=C stretch), 1424.0 (C–C stretch skeletal bands), 1424.0 (C=N stretch), 1162.0 cm^{-1} (C–N stretch); ^1H NMR (DMSO- d_6) δ : 3.70 ppm (3H, s, –OCH₃), 4.54 (1H, s, NH), 6.57 (2H, d, $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{COOH}$), 6.68 (1H, s, CH), 6.85 (2H, d, *p*-hydroxybenzaldehyde), 7.26 (2H, t, ArH), 7.54 (1H, d, *p*-hydroxybenzaldehyde), 7.64 (2H, d, ArH), 7.92 (2H, d, $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{COOH}$), 8.08 (1H, s, ArH), 10.14 (1H, s, –CHO), 10.86 (1H, s, –COOH).

***N,N*-Diethylaminomethyl-2-methylbenzimidazole (2a)** : To a solution containing compound 2 (1.31 g, 10.0 mmol) in 20 ml of ethanol, 1.03 ml (10.0 mmol) of diethylamine and 0.27 ml (10.0 mmol) of 37% formaldehyde were added with stirring for 1 h. The reaction mixture was refluxed for 20 min. On cooling, the product formed was filtered, dried in vacuum and recrystallized from ethanol to give compound 2a (64.97%), m.p. 152–154 °C (Found : C, 71.85; H, 8.72; N, 19.38. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{19}\text{N}_3$: C, 71.88; H, 8.75; N, 19.35%); UV λ_{max} (DMSO) : 276.5 nm; IR (KBr) ν_{max} : 3061.1 (Ar–C–H stretch), 2916.1 (C–H asym. stretch –CH₃), 2846.0 (C–H sym. stretch CH₂), 1588.9 (ring C=C), 1449.4 (C=N stretch), 1353.3 (C–N stretch 3° amine), 1269.0 cm^{-1} (C–N stretch); ^1H NMR (DMSO- d_6) δ : 0.94 ppm (6H, t, (CH₃)₂), 2.34

(3H, s, CH₃), 2.44 (4H, q, (CH₂)₂), 4.89 (2H, s, CH₂), 7.25 (2H, d, ArH), 7.63 (2H, t, ArH).

***N,N*-Dimethylaminomethyl-2-methylbenzimidazole (2b)** : To a solution containing compound 2 (1.31 g, 10.0 mmol) in 20 ml of ethanol, 0.50 ml (10.0 mmol) of dimethylamine and 0.27 ml (10.0 mmol) of 37% formaldehyde were added with stirring for 1 h. The reaction mixture was refluxed for 20 min. On cooling, the product formed was filtered, dried in vacuum and recrystallized from ethanol to give compound 2b (66.66%), m.p. 129–131 °C (Found : C, 69.81; H, 7.97; N, 22.19. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{15}\text{N}_3$: C, 69.84; H, 7.93; N, 22.22%); UV λ_{max} (DMSO) : 256.0 nm; IR (KBr) ν_{max} : 3061.5 (Ar–C–H stretch), 2916.2 (C–H asym. stretch –CH₃), 2848.5 (C–H sym. stretch CH₂), 1554.0 (ring C=C stretch), 1449.6 (C=N stretch), 1354.1 (C–N stretch 3° amine), 1150.5 cm^{-1} (C–N stretch); ^1H NMR (DMSO- d_6) δ : 2.20 ppm (6H, s, (CH₃)₂), 2.50 (3H, s, –CH₃), 4.72 (2H, s, CH₂), 7.52 (2H, d, ArH), 7.75 (2H, t, ArH).

***N,N*-Diphenylaminomethyl-2-methylbenzimidazole (2c)** : To a solution containing compound 2 (1.31 g, 10.0 mmol) in 20 ml of ethanol, 1.69 g (10.0 mmol) of diphenyldiamine and 0.27 ml (10.0 mmol) of 37% formaldehyde were added with stirring for 1 h. The reaction mixture was refluxed for 20 min. On cooling, the product formed was filtered, dried in vacuum and recrystallized from methanol to give compound 2c (67.02%), m.p. 171–173 °C (Found : C, 80.54; H, 6.04; N, 13.38. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{19}\text{N}_3$: C, 80.51; H, 6.07; N, 13.41%); UV λ_{max} (DMSO) : 308.7 nm; IR (KBr) ν_{max} : 3053.0 (Ar–C–H stretch), 2847.8 (C–H sym. stretch –CH₃), 2721.0 (C–H sym. stretch CH₂), 1589.9 (ring C=C stretch), 1450.0 (C=N stretch), 1349.3 (C–N stretch 3° amine), 1221.3 cm^{-1} (C–N stretch); ^1H NMR (DMSO- d_6) δ : 2.43 ppm (3H, s, CH₃), 5.59 (2H, s, CH₂), 6.96 (2H, t, –C₆H₅), 7.05 (4H, t, –C₆H₅), 7.12 (4H, d, –C₆H₅), 7.69 (2H, d, ArH).

***N,N*-Diethylaminomethyl-2-benzylbenzimidazole (3a)** : To a solution containing compound 3 (1.81 g, 10.0 mmol), 20 ml ethanol, 1.03 ml (10.0 mmol) of diethylamine and 0.27 ml (10 mmol) of 37% formaldehyde were added with stirring for 1 h. Then the reaction mixture was refluxed for 20 min. On cooling, the product formed was filtered, dried in vacuum and recrystallized from ethanol

to give compound **3a** (69.34%), m.p. 141–143 °C (Found : C, 77.86; H, 7.83; N, 14.37. Calcd. for $C_{19}H_{23}N_3$: C, 77.81; H, 7.80; N, 14.33%); UV λ_{\max} (DMSO) : 234.0 nm; IR (KBr) ν_{\max} : 3048.0 (Ar-C-H stretch), 2834.0 (C-H sym. stretch CH_2), 1586.0 (ring C=C stretch), 1456.0 (C=N stretch), 1315.3 (C-N stretch 3° amine), 1221.3 cm^{-1} (C-N stretch); 1H NMR (DMSO- d_6) δ : 1.20 ppm (6H, t, $(CH_3)_2$), 2.58 (4H, q, $(CH_2)_2$), 3.82 (2H, s, CH_2), 4.82 (2H, s, CH_2 of benzyl), 7.06 (2H, d, $-C_6H_5$), 7.11 (1H, t, $-C_6H_5$), 7.52 (2H, t, $-C_6H_5$), 7.63 (2H, t, ArH), 7.88 (2H, d, ArH).

N,N-Dimethylaminomethyl-2-benzylbenzimidazole (**3b**) : To a solution containing compound **3** (1.81 g, 10.0 mmol), 20 ml ethanol, 0.50 ml (10.0 mmol) of dimethylamine and 0.27 ml (10.0 mmol) of 37% formaldehyde were added with stirring for 1 h. The reaction mixture was refluxed for 20 min. On cooling, the product formed was filtered, dried in vacuum and recrystallized from ethanol to give compound **3b** (66.09%), m.p. 155–157 °C (Found : C, 76.94; H, 7.12; N, 15.81. Calcd. for $C_{17}H_{19}N_3$: C, 76.98; H, 7.16; N, 15.84%); UV λ_{\max} (DMSO) : 210.0 nm; IR (KBr) ν_{\max} : 3114.2 (Ar-C-H stretch), 2834.5 (C-H sym. stretch CH_2), 1586.0 (ring C=C stretch), 1453.0 (C=N stretch), 1318.0 (C-N stretch 3° amine), 1132.2 cm^{-1} (C-N stretch); 1H NMR (DMSO- d_6) δ : 2.58 ppm (6H, s, $(CH_3)_2$), 3.82 (2H, s, CH_2 of benzyl), 4.82 (2H, s, CH_2), 7.06 (2H, d, $-C_6H_5$), 7.11 (1H, t, $-C_6H_5$), 7.52 (2H, t, $-C_6H_5$), 7.63 (2H, t, ArH), 7.88 (2H, d, ArH).

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